

REKREATION TURIZM KARTALARI TIZIMINI YARATISHNI ILMIY
ASOSLASH PRINSIPLARI.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7831934>

Ergasheva Ma'muraxon Abduqosim qizi
Farg'ona politexnika institute magistri

Rekreasion turizm maqsadlari uchun o'zaro bog'liq va bir-birini to'ldiradigan kartografik asarlar tizimini yaratish muammosi mamlakatimiz oldida to'laligicha xalq qilinmagan. Bu borada olib borilgan maqsadli tadqiqotlardan ma'lum bo'ldiki dastavval turizmni mavzuli kartaga olish prinsiplarini shakllantirish zarurligini aniqlandi. Prinsip tushinichi keng ma'noda yetakchi va yo'naltiruvchi g'oya kabi talqin qilinadi, ilmiy ma'noda esa u muayyan ilmiy tizimli yo'nalish negizida yotadi [1-5].

Rekreasion turizm mavzusiga oid nashr qilingan kartografik asarlar tahlili bo'yicha turizm resurslari va murakkab tashkil etilgan turistik-rekreasion tizimlarining asosiy xususiyatlarini quyidagicha izohlash lozim. Turizm maqsadlari uchun tizimli kartaga olishda butunlik, tanlash, aniq maqsadga qaratilganlik, tizim dekompozitsiyasi, tizimlilik, iyerarxialiligi bilan izohlandi [6-10]. Turizmni kartaga olishning bunday izohlanishi bilan sinxron ravishda turistik kartalarni yaratishning umumiy prinsiplarini shakllantirish imkonini berdi (1-rasm).

Turizmni kartaga olishning umumiy prinsiplari quyidagicha ifodalandi:

- butunlik prinsipi bir butun ta'lim tizimi kabi turistik- rekreasion tizimli kartaga olish, turistik infratuzilma, turizm rivojlanishi shartlari va resurslari zaruriyati tufayli ifodalanadi, hududiy-resursli, tanishuv, rekreasion va iqtisodiy soha orqali batafsil o'rganishni talab qiladi;

- tanlash prinsipi tizimning turistik mavzuli kartografik mahsulotning iste'molchilari uchun qiziqarli barcha elementlarini tanlash zarurligini isbotlaydi;

- aniq maqsadga qaratilgan hududni o'rganishda tadqiqot aniq parametrlar asosida turizmni rivojlantirish muayyan darajada hudud sharoitlari va resurslariga bog'liq, turizm maqsadlari uchun kartaga olish iste'molchilar uchun qiziqarli ma'lumotlar bilan ta'minlashga, o'zbek xalqining o'ziga xosligi, tarixiy, me'moriy, madaniy obidalarga ega ko'p asrlik madaniyat qatlamiga qaratilishi lozim;

1-rasm. Turizm planlari, kartalari va atlaslari yaratishning umumiy prinsiplari.

- dekompozitsiya prinsipi barcha bosqichlarda maqsadga muvofiqlik tizimning alohida elementlari (turistik infratuzilma yodgorliklari yoki obyektlari) yoki alohida mavzuli tizim elementlariga (arxitektura, adabiyot, adabiy san'at va boshqa.) asoslangan;

- iyerarxiklik prinsipi tadqiqot obyektining bir butun jamlangan ko'p bosqichli ta'lim sifatida ko'rib chiqishni taxmin qiladi, chunki u geotizim kartografik modelining mantiqiy va axborot mutanosibligini anglatadi;

- tizimlilik prinsipi tadqiqot obyektining tarkibiy qismlarini alohida o'rganadi, shu sababli turistik kartografik asarlarda legendalar uning asosiy mazmuni tashkil qiladi [11-15]. Bu holatda asosiy bo'g'inlari vazifasini hududning tabiiy, biomadaniy, tarixiy-madaniy, sosial- iqtisodiy resurslari, milliy an'analar, xalq ijodi va o'ziga xosligi bilan izohlanadi. Bu tarkibning keyingi mufassal taqsimlanishi tadqiqotning quyidagi turistik-rekreasion tizimi kichikroq elementlarini ajratib beradi.

Respublikada turizm bo'yicha olib borilayotgan davlat siyosati uning taraqqiyoti va kartografik ta'minotini zamonaviy tendensiyalar negizida bajarish lozimligini anglatmoqda [6]. Mamlakatda turizmning rivojlanishi bilan bir qatorda turistik plan, karta va atlaslari xilma- xilligini ta'minlashni ilmiy asoslash zaruratini ko'rsatmoqda. Turizmni kartografik ta'minlash hamda ularning kartografik tizimini ishlab chiqish turistik resurslardan foydalanish tasnifi, holati va muhofazasi haqida ma'lumotni aks ettiradigan mavzuli kartografik asarlar tizimlashgan holda yaratilmagan [16-20].

Turizm maqsadlari uchun mintaqaviy kartaga olishni ilmiy asoslarini ishlab chiqish jarayonida turizmni kartaga olishning tizimlilik prinsipiga alohida ahamiyat qaratiladi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR:

1. Yusufovich G. Y., Shavkat o'g'li S. Y. CARTOGRAPHIC RESOURCES USED IN THE CREATION OF ELECTRONIC AGRICULTURAL MAPS OF FERGANA REGION //Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. – 2023. – T. 11. – №. 3. – C. 1001-1009.
2. Abduvakhobovich A. A., Shavkat o'g'li S. Y. IMPROVING THE METHOD OF MAPPING AGRICULTURE USING REMOTE SENSING DATA //Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. – 2023. – T. 11. – №. 3. – C. 1093-1100.
3. Khakimova K., Yokubov S. CREATION OF AGRICULTURAL ELECTRONIC MAPS USING GEOINNOVATION METHODS AND TECHNOLOGIES //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D1. – C. 64-71.
4. qizi Olimova D. S. et al. THEORETICAL BASIS FOR THE USE OF MODERN GIS TECHNOLOGIES IN THE CREATION OF NATURAL CARDS //RESEARCH AND EDUCATION. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 4-10.
5. Mavlyankulova S. Z. et al. THE ESSENCE OF CARTOGRAPHIC MAPS IS THAT THEY ARE USED FOR CARTOGRAPHIC DESCRIPTION OF THE TERRAIN. GENERALIZING WORKS IN THE PREPARATION OF MAPS //RESEARCH AND EDUCATION. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 27-33.
6. Alakhanov Z. M. et al. THE STATE CADASTRE FOR THE REGULATION OF INFORMATION RESOURCES FOR THE FORMATION AND IMPROVEMENT //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 47-53.
7. Shavkat o'g'li Y. S., Zuxriddinovna M. S., Qizi O. D. S. ARC Create an Agricultural Card in GIS and Panorama Applications //Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 6. – C. 429-434.
8. Arabboevna A. M., Shavkat o'g'li Y. S. The Use of Geoinformation Systems in the Study of the Land Fund of Household and Dekhkan Farms //Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. – 2022. – T. 8. – C. 163-164.
9. Khakimova K. R. et al. SOME TECHNOLOGICAL ISSUES OF USING GIS IN MAPPING OF IRRIGATED LANDS //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 4. – C. 226-233.
10. O'G'Li S. Y. S., Zuxriddinovna M. S., Qizi A. S. B. THE USE OF MAPINFO PROGRAM METHODS IN THE CREATION OF CADASTRAL CARDS //Science and innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. A3. – C. 278-283.

11. Mamatqulov O., Qobilov S., Yokubov S. CULTIVATION OF MEDICINAL SAFFRON PLANT IN THE SOIL COVER OF FERGANA REGION //Science and Innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 7. – C. 240-244.
12. Valievich M. X., Bakhodirjon o'g'li M. B. LARGE-SCALE ENGINEERING AND TOPOGRAPHIC PLANS //Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. – 2023. – T. 11. – №. 3. – C. 1119-1125.
13. Arabboyevna A. M. et al. CREATION OF A SATELLITE GEODESIC BASE ON THE TERRITORY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN //Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. – 2023. – T. 11. – №. 3. – C. 1033-1039.
14. Musimovich S. M. et al. THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL ISSUES IN CREATING POPULATION EMPLOYMENT MAPS USING GIS SOFTWARE //Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. – 2023. – T. 11. – №. 3. – C. 1060-1068.
15. Shavkat o'g'li Y. S., Avazbek o'g'li A. A. Ways to Improve the Application of Cartographic Research Method in the Development and Equipment of Land Resources Cards //Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 7. – C. 139-145.
16. Mavlyankulova S. Z. et al. THE ESSENCE AND FUNCTIONS OF CREATING A CARD, CHOOSING A METHOD FOR CREATING A CARD //INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 3-8.
17. qizi Olimova D. S. et al. THE ESSENCE AND FUNCTIONS OF CREATING A CARD, CHOOSING A METHOD FOR CREATING A CARD //INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 137-143.
18. Berdaliyeva Y. X. et al. Gis Dasturlari Yordamida Geografik Asos Qatlamlarini Joylashtirish Va Ularni Boshqarish //INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON LEARNING AND TEACHING. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 6. – C. 312-314.
19. Mamatqulov O., Qobilov S., Yokubov S. FARG 'ONA VILOYATINING TUPROQ QOPLAMIDA DORIVOR ZAFARON O 'SIMLIGINI YETISHTRISH //Science and innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. D7. – C. 240-244.
20. Abboskhonovich M. A. et al. PROCESSES OF INTRODUCING THE DIGITAL ECONOMY ON IRRIGATED LAND //Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. – 2023. – T. 11. – №. 3. – C. 1126-1131.